

The new replacement name *Euafricana* nom. nov. for the preoccupied genus *Africana* Ocaña & Brito, 2015 (Cnidaria: Anthozoa: Scleractinia: Caryophylliidae)

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<http://zoobank.org/A6261519-EAB4-4620-BDDD-08626D453CAF>

Abstract: The genus name *Euafricana* Ceccolini & Cianferoni **nom. nov.** is proposed to replace the name of the coral *Africana* Ocaña & Brito, preoccupied by the nematode genus *Africana* Travossos, 1920. *Euafricana wirtzi* (Ocaña & Brito, 2015) **comb. nov.** is also established.

Keywords: Cnidaria, Heterakidae, new combination, nomen novum

The genus name *Africana* was used twice in zoological nomenclature. Recently, Ocaña & Brito in Ocaña et al. (2015: 60) established a new genus using this name to allocate the new species *A. wirtzi*. The latter is an anthozoan described through a single colony from Santiago island in Cape Verde archipelago; it is included in Caryophylliidae with a peculiar mix of characters that makes it different from the other genera of the family: the presence of a solid corallum joined to the septal junction arrangement and pali presence (see Cairns & Kitahara, 2012; Ocaña et al., 2015). The name is currently accepted (Rees, 2021; WoRMS Editorial Board, 2021).

Unfortunately, the same name had already been used for a new nematode genus by Travossos (1920: 48) to transfer three species from the genus *Heterakis* Dujardin, 1844. The name *Africana* Travossos, 1920 is currently accepted within Ascaridomorpha Heterakidae, including 10 species parasites of amphibians and reptiles distributed in Africa and the Neotropical region

(see Bouamer & Morand, 2008; Ávila & da Silva, 2009). Thus, the genus *Africana* Ocaña & Brito is a junior homonym of the genus name *Africana* Travossos and, according to the ICZN (1999, Article 60), since no synonyms are available (see ICZN, 1999, Art. 60.3), it should be replaced with a new name.

Replacement name

Herein we propose the name *Euafricana* Ceccolini & Cianferoni **nom. nov.** This genus is monotypic and consequently the only species *Africana wirtzi* Ocaña & Brito, 2015 is its type species.

Etymology

The new name follows the original one, adding the prefix *eu-* (from the greek εὖ = true) since this genus really

includes only African species, while its senior homonym *Africana* Travassos, 1920 currently includes also some American species. The gender of the new name is feminine.

Systematics

Class ANTHOZOA Ehrenberg, 1834
Order SCLERACTINIA Bourne, 1900
Family CARYOPHYLLIIDAE Gray, 1847
Genus *Euafricana* Ceccolini & Cianferoni **nom. nov.**
Species *Euafricana wirtzi* (Ocaña & Brito, 2015)
comb. nov. = *Africana wirtzi* Ocaña & Brito, 2015
(type species)

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